

INVESTIGATION OF A PVC DISCRIMINATION SYSTEM USING NEAR-INFRARED LIGHT

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In many waste disposal plants, it is difficult to accurately sort polyvinyl chloride (PVC) from other plastics. PVC is widely used in pipes and vinyl sheets, but generates harmful substances during combustion and cannot be recycled together with other resins. Therefore, efficient separation of PVC from mixed waste is essential for sustainable waste management and for reducing environmental pollution. Manual sorting is labor-intensive and inconsistent, highlighting the need for an automated and reliable discrimination method. This study aims to develop an automated discrimination system using near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy to identify PVC quickly and accurately. NIR spectroscopy irradiates the sample with near-infrared light and analyzes the reflected spectrum to determine material characteristics. Previous studies have shown that the reflection spectra vary depending on the plastic type, allowing for material-specific identification. In this research, reflected light in the wavelength range considered effective for PVC discrimination was collected from several plastic samples. Experiments using white plastic specimens confirmed a distinct reflectance characteristic of PVC in the 1000–1150 nm wavelength range, consistent with known absorption features of chlorine-containing polymers. Further experiments investigated the effect of color on reflectance characteristics by irradiating ten colored PVC samples and measuring reflected intensity with a photodiode. The results revealed that while reflectance patterns were similar for light-colored PVC (e.g., white and lemonade), color variation caused noticeable differences in the 1000–1150 nm range. In contrast, transmittance measurements showed almost identical spectral behavior regardless of color, suggesting that transmittance characteristics are largely color-independent and may provide a more stable basis for discrimination. These findings indicate that color influences reflectance-based discrimination and must be considered in system design. Future work will focus on compensating for color effects, optimizing illumination and detection conditions, and exploring transmittance-based discrimination methods combined with machine learning to improve overall identification accuracy and robustness.

Keywords: PVC sorting, Near-infrared spectroscopy, Plastic sorting, Waste management

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